

SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF TRAUMATIC TRICEPS TENDON AVULSION IN CATS USING A NEW UHMWPE IMPLANT: A CASE REPORT

F. Fauqueux*¹, B. Goin^{2,3,4}

¹ Clinique vétérinaire Animed, Gap, France

² Université de Lyon, VetAgro Sup, Service de chirurgie des petits animaux, Interactions Cellules Environnement (ICE), Marcy l'Etoile, France

³ Novetech Surgery, Monaco

⁴ Univ Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, Univ Gustave Eiffel, IFSTTAR, LBMC UMR_T 9406, Lyon, France

Contact: fauqueux@animed.fr

Introduction

Triceps tendon disruption is a relatively rare tendon disorder in both dogs and cats¹. It is as disabling for the animal as it is difficult to manage for the surgeon. Conventional repair techniques consist in re-apposition of the tendon ends by tendon suturing and long immobilization of the affected limb by an external fixator, which can induce many postoperative complications. The objective of this case report is to clinically evaluate the surgical technique published by Buttin and colleagues in 2020², in a case of triceps tendon avulsion in a cat performed without postoperative immobilization of the affected limb.

Case report

A 13-month-old European female cat weighing 4.5 kg, who suffered a fall from a balcony three weeks before presentation. Despite anti-inflammatory treatment, severe lameness persisted in the right forelimb. During a second consultation with her attending veterinarian, she was diagnosed with traumatic tendon tearing of the triceps on its olecranon insertion. The case was then referred to us for surgery. A LOAD questionnaire was completed with the owner of the animal during the preoperative consultation, with a score of 30/52 indicating severe impairment of its mobility³. An ultrasound confirmed a complete triceps tendon rupture. The x-ray showed the presence of a bone fragment in the level of distal and caudal third of the humerus, corresponding to the area of insertion of the triceps tendon onto the olecranon.

The cat was anesthetized (tiletamine (0.5 mg / kg) / zolazepam (0.5 mg / kg) + medetomidine (0.01 mg / kg) + morphine hydrochloride (0.5 mg / kg) by induction. An isoflurane relay (between 0.8 and 1%) in open circuit was carried out at a flow rate of 1L / min. A constant rate infusion (1ml / kg / h) of a mixture of 250 ml of physiological serum + 30 mg of morphine + 202.75 mg of lidocaine + 75 mg of ketamine was administered. A single injection of cephalexin at 30 mg / kg was given at the start of surgical preparation.

Surgical technique

The cat was placed in left lateral decubitus. Classical disinfection of the pathological limb was carried out with chlorhexidine. A latero-caudal surgical approach was used so that the surgical wound would not interfere with the UHMWPE prosthesis once implanted. After dissection of the fleshy body of the triceps and

debridement of the tendon, distal avulsion of the triceps tendon was observed, thus confirming the diagnosis made during the clinical examination. An incision of the medial head of the triceps tendon up into the muscle body was performed: it was 6-cm long and one third of the tendon depth. The UHMWPE implant (Novaten[®] 4000, Novetech Surgery, Monaco) was placed inside the incision right down to the muscle body, which was then sutured using three metric PDS sutures.

A first 2.7-mm tunnel was drilled through the olecranon on a distally and laterally directed axis. A second tunnel, where the implant was locked, was then drilled with a 3.2-mm cannulated drill bit after having previously implanted a 1-mm guide wire from the lateral face towards the medial face of the proximal ulna along the caudo-cranial axis. The location of this borehole was chosen to guarantee a sufficient bone safety margin on both sides of the tunnel, in order to reduce the risk of splitting lines when inserting the interference screw into the tunnel. The interference screw (4 x 13 mm) chosen to lock the implant was implanted empty into the second borehole, and then withdrawn in order to create a bore. Using a guide wire, the implant was slid into the first borehole and then into the second. The implant was kept taut with the help of a clamp. The elbow was then mobilized to choose the optimal tension. Once it was found, the interference screw was implanted in the second borehole, previously reamed. The excess of implant was removed with a scalpel. Abundant rinsing with physiological serum was carried out. Tendon ends were then reapplied one in front of the other, thanks to a Kessler suture using three metric PDS. The surgical wound was closed plan by plan. Postoperative radiographs showed a satisfactory position of the tunnels and a good implantation of the interference screw along the axis of the second drilling.

Postoperative management

Immediate postoperative follow-up

No external restraint of the operated limb was performed. The animal's activity was restricted, with a ban on going outside. An anti-inflammatory treatment based on meloxicam (0.05 mg / kg) was prescribed for 6 days, in addition to a fentanyl patch (12 µg / h).

On D + 1, the cat used her operated limb during walking.

15-day postoperative follow-up

The cat walked with mild lameness and performed jumps and landings with no increased lameness. On clinical examination, a moderate reaction was noted during pronation / supination of the operated limb. No pain was noted during pressure / palpation of the triceps. The x-ray showed a good evolution of the bone healing process.

45-day postoperative follow-up

The cat had resumed normal life, with only slight lameness during waking reported by the owner, as well as the habit of standing still with the operated paw slightly raised. No pain was evident. The x-ray did not show any loosening of the implant and the ultrasound did not reveal any inflammation around the prosthesis.

4-month postoperative follow-up

A LOAD questionnaire was completed by the owner of the animal, with a score of 5/52 indicating a slight impairment of cat's mobility³.

Discussion

The surgical management of triceps tendon rupture in dogs¹ and cats^{1,4} has scarcely been described in the literature. To our knowledge, no study has yet been published on a technique that avoids the immobilization of the operated limb during the postoperative period. The study published by Buttin and colleagues in 2020 suggested this possibility without having tried it². Since then, the same authors have published a biomechanical study on this technique, reporting a better resistance to pullout than in all other conventional tendon repairs⁵. We chose to perform this technique in order to reduce the risk of complications related to the installation of an external fixator, as with other conventional techniques^{1,4}.

The interference screw (4 x 13 mm) used in this surgery proved to be oversized for a cat. As no smaller reference has yet been marketed by the manufacturer, it is difficult to set up and increases the risk of a split line when it is implanted in cats. A 2.5- or 3-mm diameter interference screw would be more suitable during such surgery.

References

1. Earley NF, Ellse G, Wallace AM, et al. Complications and outcomes associated with 13 cases of triceps tendon disruption in dogs and cats (2003–2014). *Vet Rec.* 2018;182(4):108-108. doi:10.1136/vr.104280
2. Buttin P, Goin B, Cachon T, Viguier E. Repair of Tendon Disruption Using a Novel Synthetic Fiber Implant in Dogs and Cats: The Surgical Procedure and Three Case Reports. *Vet Med Int.* 2020;2020:1-9. doi:10.1155/2020/4146790
3. Walton MB, Cowderoy E, Lascelles D, Innes JF. Evaluation of Construct and Criterion Validity for the 'Liverpool Osteoarthritis in Dogs' (LOAD) Clinical Metrology Instrument and Comparison to Two Other Instruments. Wade C, ed. *PLoS ONE.* 2013;8(3):e58125. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0058125
4. Liehmann L, Lorinson D. Traumatic triceps tendon avulsion in a cat. *J Small Anim Pract.* 2006;47(2):94-97. doi:10.1111/j.1748-5827.2006.00037.x
5. Buttin P, Goin B, Giraud N, Viguier E, Cachon T. Biomechanical analysis of an original repair of an achilles tendon rupture in dogs: preliminary results. *Comput Methods Biomech Biomed Engin.* 2020;23(sup1):S52-S54. doi:10.1080/10255842.2020.1812157